

CALL FOR PAPERS

Generative Artificial Intelligence, Synthetic Data, and Synthetic Respondents in Marketing and Market Research

IMPORTANT DEADLINES

- Submission of Full Paper: until September 30, 2026
- Initial decision sent to authors: by November 30, 2026
- Deadline for revised papers: February 10, 2027
- Notification of acceptance: by March 31, 2027
- Deadline for final versions: April 30, 2027

GUEST EDITORS

- Eduardo Mesquita – Escola Superior de Propaganda e Marketing (ESPM), Brazil (eduardo.mesquita@espm.br)
- Marcelo L. D. S. Gabriel – Escola Superior de Propaganda e Marketing (ESPM), Brazil (marcelo.gabriel@espm.br)
- Evandro L. Lopes - Escola Superior de Propaganda e Marketing (ESPM), Brazil (evandro.lopes@espm.br)
- Joseph F. Hair Jr. - University of South Alabama (USA), United States (jhair@southalabama.edu)
- Misty Sabol - University of South Alabama (USA), United States (msabol@southalabama.edu)

BAR EDITOR-IN-CHIEF

- Ricardo Limongi – Universidade Federal de Goiás, Brazil (ricardolimongi@ufg.br)

CONTEXT AND RATIONALE

Decision-oriented empirical research in marketing and management is undergoing a structural transformation. Advances in generative artificial intelligence, particularly large language models (LLMs), have opened the possibility that empirical evidence itself can be partially constructed, expanded, or stress-tested by generating valid and meaningful synthetic data and synthetic respondents. These developments promise substantial gains in speed, scale, and cost efficiency in obtaining useful data, while enabling empirical inquiry into populations that are rare, sensitive, geographically dispersed, or otherwise difficult to access.

Importantly, the diffusion of synthetic data practices is not confined to academic experimentation. Commercial research providers and analytics platforms are increasingly incorporating synthetic personas (respondents), hybrid samples, and automated iteration routines into their workflows, often blending human and AI-generated data in ways that are not yet well understood or consistently governed (Argyle et al., 2023; Bisbee et al., 2024). While computational simulations have long been discussed in the methodological literature as tools for theory testing and robustness analysis (Davis et al., 2007; Leavitt et al., 2021; Olenick & Outland, 2025), the rise of generative models fundamentally alters the nature of this discussion. Unlike parameter-driven simulations grounded in explicitly defined population models, LLM-based systems can generate data through probabilistic architectures trained on vast, opaque datasets, introducing new intellectual and organizational challenges, such as assessing the validity and reliability of the data (Bisbee et al., 2024).

The central question facing scholars and scientists, therefore, is no longer whether synthetic data and respondents will be used, but under what conditions they are appropriate, for which research purposes, with what risks, and under which standards of validation, reliability, transparency, and accountability. These questions are not merely technical. They are deeply organizational and institutional, shaping how evidence is obtained and evaluated, how decisions are justified, and how responsibility for knowledge claims is distributed and confirmed within organizations and research ecosystems.

This Special Issue of the *Brazilian Administration Review* invites contributions that treat synthetic data and synthetic respondents as a joint challenge and problem of theory, methods, governance, and, ultimately, acceptance. Beyond consumer-level applications, we particularly encourage research that examines how executives, managers, analysts, and academic scholars assess the credibility of AI-generated or AI-augmented evidence, how such assessments interact with organizational risk, compliance, and accountability structures, and how they ultimately influence strategic and tactical decision-making.

Recent work in marketing and consumer research emphasizes that LLM-generated ‘silicon samples’ may be most appropriate for exploratory and preparatory research stages but pose substantial risks to confirmatory inference and subgroup analysis if used uncritically (Sarstedt et al., 2024). Furthermore, recent research demonstrates that while LLM-generated data may approximate central tendencies observed in human samples, it likely exhibits reduced variance, sensitivity to AI prompt design, instability over time, and systematic distortions across subgroups, and therefore raises concerns for inference, generalization, and reproducibility (Bisbee et al., 2024; Dominguez-Olmedo et al., 2024). At the same time, work on technological agency and perceived controls to ensure data quality suggests that acceptance of algorithmic outputs depends not only on statistical performance but also on users’ perceptions of transparency, participation, and controllability in the data generation process (Sundar & Marathe, 2010). Parallel debates are also emerging around disclosure norms and responsible use of generative AI in academic and competitive research, as universities, organizations, and journals struggle to define consistent expectations for transparency and accountability (Hair & Sabol, 2024). An improved understanding of when and how these technical and perceptual dimensions jointly shape organizational adoption is, therefore, a central objective of this Special Issue.

THEMATIC FRAMEWORK

We welcome empirical, conceptual, and methodological contributions addressing one or more of the following themes:

1. Credibility and organizational adoption of synthetic evidence

Research examining how managers, executives, and analysts attribute credibility, trust, and legitimacy to evidence produced or amplified by generative AI, and how these judgments translate or fail to translate into strategic action. Particular attention is given to contexts involving high uncertainty, reputational exposure, and asymmetric error costs (Schilke & Reimann, 2025). Contributions may explore validation practices, transparency, auditability mechanisms, AI literacy, and interdepartmental tensions (e.g., marketing, insights, legal, compliance), as well as the role of perceived agency and control in shaping acceptance (Sundar & Marathe, 2010).

2. Appropriateness and boundary conditions by research purpose

Research explicitly delineating when synthetic data and respondents are suitable for exploratory analysis, rapid iteration, pretesting, and scenario analysis, versus when their use may compromise inference, forecasting accuracy, or subgroup sensitivity. Comparative work assessing human, synthetic, and hybrid samples and proposing purpose-specific criteria for use is especially encouraged, particularly when linked to concrete managerial consequences (Dominguez-Olmedo et al., 2024).

3. Data quality, bias, and decision consequences

Investigations into how synthetic data generation may amplify existing biases, compress distributions, attenuate extremes, or distort multivariate relationships, and how these distortions affect downstream decisions in areas such as segmentation, positioning, pricing, communication, customer experience, and resource allocation. Contributions should make explicit the decision implications, including risks of overconfidence, error asymmetries, and strategic misalignment. Unlike traditional simulations, LLM-generated data may reproduce plausible patterns without transparent generative assumptions, raising unique challenges for diagnosis and correction (Bisbee et al., 2024).

4. Governance, accountability, and the synthetic evidence lifecycle

Research addressing how organizations define standards for documentation, validation, disclosure, and accountability when empirical inputs are partially generated by AI systems. Topics of interest include internal governance arrangements, auditing practices, validation controls, vendor contractual standards, and the role of transparency in establishing legitimacy. Issues of privacy, control, and decision authority are particularly salient when generative mechanisms are not fully interpretable by users (Sundar & Marathe, 2010).

5. Implications for knowledge production in marketing and related fields

Conceptual and empirical work exploring how the availability of synthetic and hybrid evidence reshapes research practices, testing and validation standards, and the relationship between theory, data, and managerial decision-making. Contributions should address, with both rigor and relevance, how organizations can harness synthetic data responsibly while maintaining robustness, transparency, and ethical accountability.

TYPES OF CONTRIBUTIONS

This Special Issue welcomes:

- Empirical articles (quantitative, qualitative, or mixed methods)
- In-depth organizational case studies
- Methodological articles proposing or evaluating validation and auditing protocols for synthetic data
- Systematic reviews or meta-analyses on synthetic data performance in marketing and management
- Conceptual essays advancing theory regarding governance, legitimacy, application, and AI-mediated knowledge

SUBMISSION PROCESS

Authors are encouraged to submit original manuscripts that follow BAR's submission guidelines by **September 30, 2026**, using the journal's **ScholarOne system**. At the first stage of submission, '**SI Generative Artificial Intelligence**' must be selected as the manuscript type. Manuscripts may be submitted in **English** or **Portuguese**. However, if a manuscript submitted in Portuguese is accepted, authors will be required to provide a full English version, ensuring both linguistic quality and consistency with the original text. Given BAR's international approach, **all accepted articles are published in English**. Submissions that are purely technical and lack explicit engagement with organizational theory, consumer and/or organizational behavior, or managerial implications fall outside the scope of this Special Issue.

Questions regarding topic suitability or eligibility may be directed to the Guest Editors prior to submission. All manuscripts will be evaluated according to BAR's editorial criteria and must follow the author guidelines available on the journal's website.

By submitting a manuscript, authors confirm that the work is original, has not been published previously, and is not under consideration by another journal, in whole or in part. Submissions must also comply with BAR's policies on plagiarism and self-plagiarism. All manuscripts are first assessed by the Guest Editors and the Editor-in-Chief. Those considered suitable are then assigned to associate editors and reviewers from BAR's editorial boards for double-blind peer review. Acceptance depends on the authors' ability to address the comments and suggestions provided by reviewers and editors.

REFERENCES

- Argyle, L. P., Busby, E. C., Fulda, N., Gubler, J. R., Rytting, C., & Wingate, D. (2023). Out of one, many: Using language models to simulate human samples. *Political Analysis*, 31(3), 337–351. <https://doi.org/10.1017/pan.2023.2>
- Bisbee, J., Clinton, J. D., Dorff, C., Kenkel, B., & Larson, J. M. (2024). Synthetic replacements for human survey data? The perils of large language models. *Political Analysis*, 32(4), 401–416. <https://doi.org/10.1017/pan.2024.5>
- Davis, J. P., Eisenhardt, K. M., & Bingham, C. B. (2007). Developing theory through simulation methods. *Academy of Management Review*, 32(2), 480–499. <https://doi.org/10.5465/amr.2007.24351453>
- Dominguez-Olmedo, R., Hardt, M., & Mendler-Dünner, C. (2024). Questioning the survey responses of large language models. *arXiv*. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2306.07951>
- Hair, J. F. Jr., & Sabol, M. (2024). Leveraging artificial intelligence (AI) in competitive intelligence (CI) research. *Journal of Sustainable Competitive Intelligence*, 15, e0469. <https://doi.org/10.24883/eagleSustainable.v15i.469>
- Leavitt, K., Schabram, K., Hariharan, P., & Barnes, C. M. (2021). Ghost in the machine: On organizational theory in the age of machine learning. *Academy of Management Review*, 46(4), 750–777. <https://doi.org/10.5465/amr.2019.0247>
- Olenick, J., & Outland, N. (2025). Artificial intelligence as theoretical workshop: Using AI to improve the theory problem in organizational sciences. *Organizational Psychology Review*. <https://doi.org/10.1177/20413866251397842>
- Sarstedt, M., Adler, S. J., Rau, L., & Schmitt, B. (2024). Using large language models to generate silicon samples in consumer and marketing research: Challenges, opportunities, and guidelines. *Psychology & Marketing*, 41(6), 1254–1270. <https://doi.org/10.1002/mar.21982>
- Schilke, O., & Reimann, M. (2025). The transparency dilemma: How AI disclosure erodes trust. *Organizational Behavior and Human Decision Processes*, 188, 104405. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.obhdp.2025.104405>
- Sundar, S. S., & Marathe, S. S. (2010). Personalization versus customization: The importance of agency, privacy, and power usage. *Human Communication Research*, 36(3), 298–322. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1468-2958.2010.01377.x>

ABOUT THE BRAZILIAN ADMINISTRATION REVIEW (BAR)

Launched in 2004 by the Brazilian Academy of Management (ANPAD), BAR has an international scope in terms of topics of interest, target audience, and editorial boards. It is an A2 journal according to the Brazilian classification Qualis/Capes (second highest rank), which is evidence of the quality of published works and the transparency of the editorial process. BAR follows the editorial principles available in the document Best Practices in Scientific Publication, an initiative by the Brazilian Academy of Management (ANPAD) to assist journals in meeting high scholarly standards and enhancing their theoretical and applied impact. BAR is also a member of COPE (Committee on Publication Ethics) and a signatory of DORA (San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment), which is additional evidence of BAR's commitment to the most rigorous ethical principles in scholarly publication.

BAR publishes documents within the interests of business and public administration, management science, and organization studies. Diverse theoretical and methodological perspectives are welcome as long as they contribute to advancing the frontiers of a specific theoretical tradition and are also insightful to practice. Prospective authors should note that studies with blurred boundaries between what is inherent to organization studies and what may be framed within the interests of, for instance, anthropology and sociology will be rejected. Symptomatically, a large body of research has been misleading organization scholars. The same policy applies to studies that are not fully characterized within another scholarly field but whose main interests concern isolated issues, such as culture, gender, race, performance, impact, and the like. BAR's editorial scope for research articles does not include teaching cases, theoretical essays, opinion papers, purely applied practitioner-oriented technical material, and replication studies. As for the latter, replication is here conceived in broad terms, including the testing of theories (confirmation/refutation of previous findings), contextualization studies (application of scales to a different context), and perspective studies (collection of data from a different demographic group). Systematic literature reviews will be considered only if they address issues of contemporary interest both for theory development and application in organizations.

BAR is aligned with Open Science practices: data, materials and open codes, in addition to the dissemination of additional information related to the editorial process. The journal is a member and subscribes to the principles of COPE - Committee for Ethics in Publications.

BAR is present in many of the most prestigious indexing platforms, such as WOS, Scopus, SciELO, Spell, Cabell's, ProQuest, DOAJ, EBSCO, Gale/Cengage Learning, IBSS, Latindex, Ullrichs, and Redalyc.

Read more about it: <https://bar.anpad.org.br>